

Smart Patient Body Parameter Recording System

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Abstract—With the growth of technology, healthcare has seen many improvements, and smart human body parameter monitoring system are important for giving better and faster care to patients. This project introduces a cloud-based Smart Patient body parameter recording system that works with a mobile application. The system is designed to constantly check the patient's important health signs and surrounding conditions. It uses smart sensors, wireless connections, and cloud storage to collect, save, and study the patient's report in actual time. The mobile app gives an easy way for physician and caregivers to see the patient's latest health information and get alerts during emergencies, even if they are not near the patient.

Today, it is the big problems in medical care is not having proper real-time monitoring, which can delay treatment and make the patient's condition worse. Our system helps solve this problem by keeping track of things like temperature of body, heart rate, room temperature, and humidity all the time. The collected input is safely transfer to cloud and shown clearly in the mobile app. This helps doctors make quick and better decisions about the patient's treatment. In this way, the system increases patient safety, improves health results, and makes healthcare monitoring easier and more accessible through mobile phones.

I. INTRODUCTION

Traditional patient monitoring methods often rely on manual checks and regular measurements done by healthcare staff. These method able to take sufficient time and may miss sudden changes in patient's situation. A smart patient body parameter recording system offers a better solution by constantly collecting and checking patient data. With real-time updates on a patient's health, doctors and nurses can take action quickly, helping to prevent serious health issues and improving the overall quality of care.

The heart is the important vital organ in the human body. It works like a pump that moves blood and oxygen throughout the body, keeping it alive and functioning properly. In today's fast-changing healthcare world, there is a growing need for smart monitoring systems that can give instant health data and alerts. This system is crucial for making quick and effective medical decisions.

This paper presents a new cloud-based smart patient body parameter recording system using a mobile application. The system continuously monitors health signs like temperature of body, heart rate, room temperature, and humidity, and sends alerts when abnormal values are detected. All the data is collected through sensors, sent via Wi-Fi, stored on the cloud, and shown on a mobile app so healthcare providers can easily view it from anywhere.

Purpose of Design Smart Human Body Parameter Monitoring System.

The proposed work aims to plan and build a Smart Patient Body Parameter Monitoring System that helps to measure body parameter of the patients. This system will mainly benefit people hose living in remote areas. This system uses smart devices and sensors to trace important health data like heart rate, body temperature, room humidity, blood pressure, room temperature and oxygen levels these sensors will be connected to a small device like a microcontroller (ESP 32) that collects the data. ESP32 has built-in Wi-Fi and Bluetooth, so it can allow to the internet easily. The collected data is transfer to the mobile app using Bluetooth or Wi-Fi.

The mobile app will be developed with a simple and user-friendly interface so that patients can use it easily. The data can be stored through cloud. The cloud acts like an online storage and processing Centre. The cloud also keeps the data safe, secure, and backed up. The proposed system provides a smart, solution to monitor patients' health parameter. The advantages of this system is that patients can be safely monitored from their homes, reducing the stay in the hospital for long periods.

Fig: Smart Patient Body Parameter Recording System

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The image display a snapshot of a “Smart Human Body Parameter Monitoring System” interface for a patient named Ganesh. It presents real time readings from various sensors:

Fig: Laptop Image

Room Temperature: 35°C
 Room Humidity: 49%
 Heart Rate: 93 BPM (Beats per Minute)
 Body Temperature: 35°C
 SpO2: 95% (Oxygen Saturation)

This system appears to be designed for monitoring a patient's vital signs and the surrounding environmental conditions. The displayed values provide a quick overview of Ganesh's current physiological state and the environment he is in. The all real time readings can be open in computer, laptop or in mobile this system access in any smart device. The above fig shows real time readings in mobile access.

Fig: Mobile Image

FUTURE SCOPE

In future, we can develop a big data base for the patients of all hospitals and these health parameters can be detect continuously, and the details is uploaded to medical server. These servers keep the information of the patient’s in the data base, and doctors can access of patient’s history, where any further consultancy happens with the doctor.

CONCLUSION

This study focuses on helping patient during medical emergencies by providing a system that allows for quick response, actual timing tracking, and continuous monitoring. In case of emergency, the system ensures the patient gets the necessary medical attention and is transported to the hospital. It also allows patients to be monitored safely and easily from their homes.

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